

Represents __%
of the citizens

Name:

Age:
Profession:
Status:
Place of Residence:

Life Situation (continuous text):

[Large empty text area for Life Situation]

Destinations (bullet marks):

-
-
-

Attitudes: (bar chart)

Personality:

reserved	outgoing
conservative	open-minded
planning	spontaneous
self-interested	cooperative

Mid-Term Needs:

inactive	active
pants pockets	bag and baggage
need for rest	tolerance for bustle
weather-sensitive	weather-resistant

On the way with:

-
-
-
-

Motto: